

An equivalent beam approach for assessing tunnelling-induced distortions of frames with infills

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Abstract

This paper presents an approach to evaluate the response of low- and medium-rise frames with continuous foundations, either with or without infills, to tunnelling employing an equivalent beam with a behaviour dominated by shear deformations. Simplified soil-structure interaction models, consisting of a beam resting on an elastic continuum half-space, are compared against advanced three-dimensional analyses in which the tunnel, the soil, and the building are explicitly modelled. In the simplified approach, the frame is schematised as a Timoshenko beam and reliable procedures to estimate both bending and shear stiffness are discussed. In the refined modelling strategy, an advanced elastoplastic constitute law is employed, capable of reproducing fairly well the soil response to the excavation for increasing values of volume loss, while the full geometry of the structure is considered. First, the results of the proposed numerical approaches are compared in terms of tunnelling-induced foundation displacements, bay deformations and maximum tensile strains in the infills. Then, for the infill panels, the reliability of estimating the maximum tensile strain from the angular distortion of the frame bays is assessed. Finally, a meta-model is proposed to predict the maximum angular distortion based on greenfield settlements, eccentricity, and relative soil-structure stiffness.

Keywords:

Tunnelling, Ground Movements, Timoshenko beam, Framed Building Response, Damage Estimation, Infills

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1 **Highlights**

- 2 • Tunnelling-induced response of low- and medium-rise frames with infills is studied
- 3 • Timoshenko beam founded on the half-space compared well with advanced simulations
- 4 • Analytical approaches for the estimate of equivalent building stiffness are described
- 5 • Angular distortion, corrected for the slab edge fixity, described well infill strains
- 6 • A meta-model for predicting the angular distortion of frames is proposed

7 **1. Introduction**

8 The excavation of tunnels inevitably induces ground deformations that can cause distortions of existing
 9 buildings. Although the effect of tunnel excavation on masonry structures has been thoroughly studied
 10 through numerical strategies with different levels of complexity (Burland et al., 1977; Son and Cording,
 11 2005; Yiu et al., 2017), including equivalent beams (Pickhaver et al., 2010) or anisotropic equivalent solids
 12 (Losacco et al., 2014, 2016), the response of framed buildings, either bare or with infill walls, have been
 13 mainly investigated with refined structural models of the building (e.g., Son (2015); Fagnoli et al. (2015);
 14 Boldini et al. (2018); Elkayam and Klar (2019)). As such, the enhancement of equivalent beam models and
 15 simplified framework to estimate tunnelling induced distortions of infilled frames has yet to be addressed.

16 The tunnel-soil-building interaction, sketched in Figure 1, is a complex phenomenon in which, among
 17 other aspects, the presence of infill panels, either stiff bearing walls or relatively flexible non-structural el-
 18 ements, can have a significant influence (Fu et al., 2018). In addition, infills are the building components
 19 most prone to suffer tunnelling-induced damage in reinforced concrete frames (Son, 2015). The angular
 20 distortion $\beta = S - w$ of a bay is given by the difference between slope S and local tilt w inferred from the
 21 corner displacements of the bay, as shown in Figure 2, to estimate its average engineering shear strain (Ritter
 22 et al., 2020). A quick damage estimate is possible by linking β to likely maximum tensile strain within the
 23 infill (Boone, 1996); however, the accuracy of this approach has not been systematically addressed. Note
 24 that the local tilt w can differ from the average slope of the building ω , inferred from the building edges, par-

Figure 1: Considered problem.

Figure 2: Bay deformation parameters.

25 ticularly in the presence of adjacent buildings (Acikgoz et al., 2021). In greenfield conditions, S_{gf} and ω_{gf}
26 are defined in Figure 2; an upper estimate of the potential for the angular distortion associated with the set-
27 tlement trough is given by the greenfield slope S_{gf} corresponding to the bay location. Recently, centrifuge
28 experiments of tunnel-soil-building interaction using bare frame models were interpreted to assess the re-
29 lationship between the modification factor for the angular distortion (i.e. the relative change of maximum
30 angular distortion with respect to the greenfield slope) and soil-structure relative stiffness (Xu et al., 2021b,
31 2020), also confirmed by numerical analyses (Boldini et al., 2021a). However, despite the evidence of the
32 possible stiffening action of wall bearing infills (Finno et al., 2005; Son, 2015; Fu et al., 2018), it is still
33 unclear how to quantify in design stages the role of the infills in the soil-structure interaction mechanism.

34 In this paper, the role of infills (either flexible or stiff masonry panels) in the tunnel-frame interaction
35 problem of low- and medium-rise buildings is addressed using two different Finite Element (FE) approaches.
36 Foundations continuous in the direction transverse to the tunnel longitudinal direction are considered. More
37 specifically, the tunnel-soil-structure interaction is simulated using both refined three-dimensional numeri-
38 cal models (employing an advanced constitutive model for the soil and accurately describing the geometry
39 of the foundations and the structural members) and a two-stage simple analysis method (based on the elas-
40 tic half-space and the Timoshenko beam theory). Foundation displacements, shear strains for each bay and
41 local tensile strains in the infills are discussed, while comparing the predictions given by the two numeri-
42 cal approaches, also in terms of modification factors. In this study, the work of Boldini et al. (2021c) is
43 further developed by extending the analyses to a much wider range of structural configurations and tunnel
44 eccentricities. Finally, a meta-model is proposed to predict the maximum angular distortion from green-
45 field settlements, frame eccentricity, and relative soil-structure stiffness. Given its simple formulation, the
46 meta-model could be easily implemented during the preliminary design stages of a project to estimate the
47 potential for the cracking of infills.

48 2. Studied scenarios

49 The investigated scenarios consist of infilled frames of varying eccentricity with respect to tunnel loca-
50 tions, as shown in Figure 1. The geometry and material properties were selected to be comparable with the
51 plane-strain experiments of tunnelling beneath bare frames performed by Xu et al. (2020) and numerically
52 simulated by Boldini et al. (2021a). However, in this paper, to directly evaluate the infill deformations and
53 their stiffening action, the structural cases are extended to frames with either flexible or stiff infills.

54 All cases consider the excavation of a tunnel with diameter $D_t = 6.12\text{m}$ and depth to the tunnel axis of
55 $z_t = 11.0\text{m}$ in dry Leighton Buzzard sand Fraction E, a well-known silica sand, with initial relative density
56 of 90%. Four different frames are considered, having either 2 or 5 storeys above ground and 3 or 6 bays,
57 resulting in a transverse width B of 15.6 or 31.3m (referred to as short and long frame in the following).
58 All frames have fixed bay length $b_{bay} = 5.2\text{m}$ and bay height $h_{bay} = 2.6\text{m}$ and structural elements (raft,
59 slabs and columns) of constant thickness ($t = 0.22\text{m}$) and Young's modulus ($E = 58\text{GPa}$). The infill
60 panels, perpendicular to the tunnel axis, are assumed either fully flexible or stiff, with a thickness of 0.25m
61 and a spacing of 8.77m in the longitudinal tunnel direction. The long frames have varying eccentricity,
62 i.e. $e/B = 0, 0.2, 0.5$, while the short frames are only modelled for $e/B = 0.5$. Therefore, eight different
63 building scenarios are considered, as summarised in Table 1.

64 For each frame and tunnel eccentricity, three types of analyses were performed: (1) *Greenfield*, with-
65 out structure (labelled as GF); (2) *Frame with flexible panels*, assuming weightless and fully-flexible infills
66 (labelled as -Flex); and (3) *Frame with stiff panels*, for which the stiffening action of the infills and their
67 weight were accounted for (labelled as -Stiff). The models including fully-flexible panels can be considered
68 as representative of bare frames, with the advantage of providing the strains in a bay as an output of the
69 analyses, hence providing both (i) a reference to assess the relative influence of infill stiffness on the ex-
70 pected damage of the building as well as (ii) deformation estimates for non-structural infill panels. A subset
71 of this study was preliminarily reported by [Boldini et al. \(2021b\)](#) and [Boldini et al. \(2021c\)](#).

Table 1: Summary of considered cases, all with either flexible or stiff panels.

	# storeys	e/B	B (m)	H (m)
Long building(*)				
2Se0L	2	0	31.3	5.2
2Se02L	2	0.2	31.3	5.2
2Se05L	2	0.5	31.3	5.2
5Se0L	5	0	31.3	13
5Se02L	5	0.2	31.3	13
5Se05L	5	0.5	31.3	13
Short building(*)				
2Se05S	2	0.5	15.6	5.2
5Se05S	5	0.5	15.6	13
(*) $b_{bay} = 5.2\text{ m}$ and $h_{bay} = 2.6\text{ m}$				

72 **3. Numerical models**

73 *3.1. Advanced analyses with solid frame models*

74 Three-dimensional (3D) FE analyses, referred to as *advanced numerical modelling*, were carried out
75 with the Plaxis software. Both ground and structural elements (frame and infills) are modelled with 10-
76 node tetrahedral solid elements. Given the constant spacing considered for the infills and the assumption of
77 plane-strain tunnelling, only a slice of the 3D prototype, with a length of 8.77m equal to the spacing between
78 panels in the longitudinal tunnel direction, was considered. To model the infills of thickness 0.25m, solid
79 panels were added to the frame in the central transverse section of the model. The simulations were run
80 modelling only half of the domain for the centred structures considering symmetry, while the full domain
81 was modelled for the eccentric buildings. An example view of the adopted Finite Element mesh for the
82 centred building is provided in Figure 3.

83 Except for the infill panels, modelling of the tunnel, ground, and bare frame is consistent with the
84 geometrical and mechanical assumptions used in [Boldini et al. \(2021a\)](#). The successful comparison of their
85 results with the data of the simulated centrifuge tests, proved the adequateness of the adopted modelling
86 strategy to investigate the problem at hand in this paper.

87 The excavation was simulated by imposing a displacement field at the tunnel boundary (constant in the
88 tunnel direction) in order to obtain a homothetic contraction of the tunnel cross-section centred on, and with
89 focus of displacement vectors pointing at, the original tunnel invert ([Boldini et al., 2018](#)). The elastoplastic
90 constitutive law SANISAND ([Dafalias and Manzari, 2004](#)) was employed for the soil, allowing to capture
91 the dependency of small-strain stiffness on the mean effective stress, the stiffness decay with strain level and
92 evolving dilatancy depending on relative density. The calibration of the material constants with laboratory
93 and centrifuge test results was performed by [Giardina et al. \(2020\)](#) and subsequently fine-tuned by [Boldini
94 et al. \(2021a\)](#); the corresponding values are summarised in Table 2. At the soil-structure contact, a frictional,
95 no-tension interface was adopted, with friction angle $\delta = 32^\circ$. An isotropic linear-elastic behaviour was
96 assumed for the structural members. For the frame, the Young's modulus $E = 53.8$ GPa, the Poisson's ratio
97 $\nu = 0.33$, the specific weight $\gamma = 27$ kN/m³ were assumed as in [Boldini et al. \(2021a\)](#), while for the stiff
98 infills the elasticity parameters were set equal to $E = 4$ GPa, $\nu = 0.2$ and $\gamma = 13$ kN/m³.

99 The advanced numerical analyses comprised the following stages: first, activation of gravity in the soil
100 domain with a coefficient of earth pressure at rest $K_0 = 0.5$, consistently with the critical state friction angle
101 of the sandy soil; then, activation of the structure and interface elements (excluded for the GF analysis);

Table 2: Adopted SANISAND constitutive model parameters.

Elasticity	$G_0 = 400; \nu = 0.05$
Critical state	$M_c = 1.287; c = 0.780; \lambda_c = 0.00178; e_0 = 0.8191; \zeta = 2.4352$
Yield surface	$m = 0.01$
Plastic modulus	$h_0 = 4.05; c_h = 1.1; n^b = 2.8$
Dilatancy	$A_0 = 0.55; n^d = 2.564$
Fabric-dilatancy tensor	$z_{max} = 0; c_z = 0$

102 finally, displacement controlled simulation of tunnel excavation.

Figure 3: Plaxis model: Finite Element discretisation of the central two-storey frame (half domain modelled).

Figure 4: ASRE two-stage analysis method: mechanical model.

103 3.2. Simplified analyses with Equivalent Beam Models

104 Two-stage continuum-based models implementing an equivalent Timoshenko beam, as shown in Fig-
 105 ure 4, displayed their reliability for masonry buildings (Franza et al., 2020). Framed structures have not
 106 been analysed yet (except for a single case study presented in Boldini et al. (2021c)). This model is suitable
 107 for a preliminary assessment considering its limited and rational list of required inputs.

108 The surface greenfield displacements obtained by the Plaxis analyses discussed in the previous section
 109 were used as input. The Young's modulus $E_s = 45\text{MPa}$ and a Poisson's ratio $\nu_s = 0.3$ were assumed
 110 for the computation of the soil compliance matrix. This E_s value represents a lower-bound value for the
 111 simulated soil conditions at $V_{l,t} < 2\%$ (Ritter, 2017; Ritter et al., 2019), estimated from greenfield average
 112 shear strain at mid-tunnel depth and the stiffness degradation curve of Fraction E sand. A friction coefficient
 113 $\mu = \tan(32^\circ)$ was adopted for the interface, as for the advanced modelling.

114 For both the "Frame with flexible panels" and "Frame with stiff panels", a lumped equivalent Timo-
 115 shenko beam model is adopted to capture the building behaviour. The cross-sectional axial stiffness EA ,

116 bending stiffness EI , and shear stiffness GA_s need to be specified; the methodology adopted to estimate
117 the equivalent stiffness, a crucial point for the findings outlined in this paper, is described in the next sec-
118 tion. Also, as shown in Figure 4, to replicate the building weight of the advanced models, a uniform line
119 load was applied to the beam so as to achieve an average contact pressure of 25kPa and 27kPa for the
120 two-storey frames with flexible and stiff infills, respectively, whereas contact pressures of 50kPa and 56kPa
121 were adopted respectively for the five-storey buildings.

122 **4. Simple closed form evaluation of the equivalent frame stiffness**

123 In order to estimate the stiffness exhibited by the structure when subject to tunnelling-induced movements
124 and to capture the shear deformations, expected to dominate in framed structure, as opposed to bending,
125 equivalent Timoshenko and laminated beams with both cross-sectional bending stiffness EI and shear stiff-
126 ness GA_s can be employed (Pickhaver et al., 2010; Franza et al., 2020; Boldini et al., 2021a). A simpler
127 approach consists of lumping the overall stiffness in a purely bending term EI_{EB} , by adopting an equivalent
128 Euler-Bernoulli beam for the structure (Franzius et al., 2006; Goh and Mair, 2014; Haji et al., 2018) that,
129 however, cannot reproduce shear deformations. Despite previous works on the definition of an equivalent
130 stiffness for simplified structural models, the contribution of infills has received limited attention (Finno
131 et al., 2005). In this paper, an analytical approach is adopted to evaluate the equivalent stiffness values EI
132 and GA_s , rather than implementing experimental or numerical procedures to reproduce loading tests of the
133 building under simplified boundary conditions (Son and Cording, 2005; Xu et al., 2020; Pickhaver et al.,
134 2010; Boldini et al., 2021a).

135 For “Frames with flexible panels”, first the equivalent bending stiffness EI and axial stiffness EA are
136 analytically obtained from the cross-sectional areas of slabs (summation of all slab areas for A and em-
137 ploying the second moment of area of each slab I_{slab} at its centroid and the parallel axis theorem with the
138 neutral axis at the middle of the building for I) as in Franzius et al. (2006). Next, the shear stiffness GA_s is
139 estimated using Equations (1) and (2). Namely, Equation (1) is obtained by matching the deflections of an
140 Euler-Bernoulli beam (with pure EI_{EB} and infinite GA_s) and the deflection of the Timoshenko beam (with
141 EI and GA_s) for a simply supported scheme under a concentrated central load. Equation (2), to estimate
142 analytically the pure bending stiffness EI_{EB} , uses the column stiffness factor of the Meyerhof theory as done
143 by Goh and Mair (2014); however, a variety of methods are available in the literature to estimate EI_{EB} (e.g.
144 Melis and Rodriguez Ortiz (2001); Haji et al. (2018)).

$$\frac{1}{GA_s} = \frac{B^2}{aEI} \left(\frac{EI}{EI_{EB}} - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

$$EI_{EB} = \sum (EI_{slab} C)_{ithfloor}; \quad C = 1 + m^2 \left(\frac{K_{LC} + K_{UC}}{K_{LC} + K_{UC} + K_B} \right) \quad (2)$$

145 where C is the column stiffening factor of the beam/slab at the i^{th} floor depending on the relative stiffness
 146 and geometry between columns and floors, I_{slab} is the second moment of area of each slab (assumed as
 147 isolated), and the summation is over all floors. The factor C of each beam/slab line is a function of the
 148 number of bays m , the average stiffness of the lower columns $K_{LC} = (I_{LC}/h)$, the average stiffness of the
 149 upper columns $K_{UC} = (I_{UC}/h)$, the average stiffness of beams $K_B = (I_b/b_{bay})_B$, while $h = (h_{LC} + h_{UC})/2$ and
 150 b_{bay} is the bay span length. Note that Equation (2) is applicable to low and medium-rise buildings, however
 151 it fails to consider that top columns in high-rise frames only marginally increase the structure stiffness at
 152 the foundation level (Haji et al., 2018).

153 For the “Frame with stiff panels”, the transformed cross-section method was applied to homogenise the
 154 section to a unique material. For this, the masonry panels were replaced by infills with a reduced thickness
 155 of 0.018 m and the material properties of the frame. Subsequently, it was assumed that in the homogenised
 156 cross-section, with $E = 53.8$ GPa and $E/G = 2.6$, the slabs contribute to the second moment of area I
 157 according to the parallel axis, the infills area were equal to the structure shear areas A_s , while both slabs and
 158 infills contribute to the area cross-sectional A . This approach is a simplified form of the laminated beam
 159 model suggested by Finno et al. (2005).

160 Table 3 summarises the properties of the Timoshenko beams associated with the long buildings, assum-
 161 ing equivalent beam with a rectangular cross-section of depth d_b . Interestingly, the comparison of these
 162 equivalent properties indicates that the infill stiffening action decreases the ratio E_b/G_b of the beam but it
 163 marginally affects the beam Young’s modulus E_b and depth d_b . In other words, the infills marginally affect
 164 the bending stiffness (depending on E_b and d_b) but they act on decreasing the shear flexibility (function of
 165 E_b/G_b). Also, a ratio between Young’s and shear moduli E_b/G_b between 100 and 600 confirms that the
 166 flexural behaviour of long buildings is dominated by shear deformations, regardless of the infill stiffness.
 167 Finally, note that the depth of the beam is slightly greater than the building total height ($d_b > H$).

Table 3: Timoshenko beam properties for the long buildings with flexible and stiff infills.

	5SL-Stiff	5SL-Flex	2SL-Stiff	2SL-Flex
E_b (GPa)	4.69	4.58	4.89	4.79
ν_b	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
E_b/G_b	107.3	575.0	133.6	599.9
d_b	15.34	15.38	7.33	7.36

168 5. Results of tunnelling-induced displacements and deformations

169 5.1. Influence of infills on the behaviour of low-rise frames

170 The effects of the infill stiffness on the interaction problem are first evaluated using the advanced mod-
 171 elling results for the two-storey structures centrally located above the tunnel, in which the symmetry of
 172 the problem prevented the building from tilting. Building deformed shapes for flexible and stiff infills are
 173 shown at $V_{l,t} = 1.0\%$ in Figure 5, while Figure 6 shows the corresponding surface soil and foundation
 174 movements. The action of the frame with flexible panels slightly decreases the settlements of the building
 175 portion directly above the tunnel, while soil settlements are nearly coincident with those computed in green-
 176 field conditions. In contrast, the presence of stiff infills induces a stiffer vertical response of the building,
 177 with a maximum foundation settlement approximately halved in comparison to the case of flexible panels
 178 and a corresponding greater gap formation at the soil-foundation interface. At the same time, regardless of
 179 the infills, there are negligible horizontal displacements at the raft intradox and slipping occurs at the soil-
 180 foundation interface because of the axial stiffness of the foundation. Also, the soil horizontal displacements
 181 under the frame with stiff panels are slightly greater in comparison to those calculated with the flexible in-
 182 fills, due to the greater pressure redistribution of the stiffer building towards the foundation edges (Boldini
 183 et al., 2018) that relates to the difference in the gap width.

184 To evaluate the two-stage Timoshenko beam model performance against Plaxis predictions, Figure 7
 185 shows foundation settlements obtained for two-storey frames centrally located and subjected to tunnelling
 186 with volume losses $V_{l,t}$ of 1 and 2%. For the simplified model, both linear elastic (EL) with perfect com-
 187 patibility at the soil-foundation and elastoplastic (EP) results allowing for gap formation are plotted. The
 188 agreement in terms of settlements between advanced and simplified beam models with the EP interface is
 189 very satisfactory for both stiff and flexible infills. Finally, as expected when gap formation can take place,
 190 elastic EL models overestimate tunnelling-induced settlements for stiff buildings and large movements. Fig-
 191 ure 7 illustrates, for the first time to the Authors' knowledge, that Timoshenko beams dominated by shear
 192 flexibility, if properly calibrated, can capture the response of framed buildings.

Figure 5: Comparison between deformed configurations: (a) flexible and (b) stiff infills ($V_{l,t} = 1.0\%$).

Figure 6: Plaxis predictions at $V_{l,t} = 1.0\%$: (a-b) vertical and (c-d) horizontal displacements for the bare frame (left) and the frames with infills (right).

193 It is of interest to quantify the tunnelling-induced angular distortion, which relates to damage. In the
 194 advanced modelling with the 3D building model, it is computed as $\beta = S - w$, where S is the average
 195 slope across the bay foundation and w is the local bay tilt (Son and Cording, 2005), as shown in Figure 2.
 196 Importantly, the considered frames with transversely continuous foundations (e.g. rafts) undergo minimal
 197 horizontal deformations due to bending and axial strains (Xu et al., 2020); thus, in these cases β describes the
 198 entire deformation level due to shearing (Ritter et al., 2020). In the Timoshenko beam models, the angular
 199 distortion β of each finite element is equal to the cross-sectional shear strain $\gamma = V/GA_s$ by definition,
 200 where V is the shear force. For simplicity, γ is evaluated continuously along the Timoshenko beam axis
 201 rather than as a mean value over the bay width. Also, greenfield values are calculated from the ground slope
 202 GS assuming no tilt (see Figure 2).

203 For the two-storey building with no eccentricity 2Se0L, β values calculated from the PLAXIS and
 204 ASRE models for $V_{l,t} = 1.0\%$ (left columns) and 2% (right columns) are shown in Figure 8. In this paper,
 205 the angular distortion β_{gf} in greenfield conditions is estimated from the slope of the settlement trough
 206 corresponding to the bay span S_{gf} (Piciullo et al., 2021) assuming local greenfield tilt $w_{gf} = 0$, which
 207 maximises the shear deformations. The values from the advanced models are plotted as markers located in

Figure 7: Plaxis and ASRE foundation settlements for the two-storey long frame (FRs2e0L).

208 correspondence with the bay mid-point along the x -axis, whereas for the Timoshenko beam the profile is a
 209 smooth line. Also, greenfield deformations are shown. Figure 8 shows that, for the considered buildings, the
 210 presence of the stiff infill panels decreases the angular distortions, particularly at the central bays subjected
 211 to the greatest greenfield ground slope. Inspection of the figure also reveals that the distortion profiles
 212 estimated by the elastoplastic simplified analyses (ASRE EP) are in excellent agreement with the advanced
 213 modelling results (Plaxis) reporting the average values across the bays (see circular markers at the bay
 214 mid-length). On the other hand, the comparison of linear elastic (ASRE EL) and elastoplastic (ASRE EP)
 215 results displays that the gap formation induces a reduction of the distortion of the central bays, together with
 216 the reduction in the settlements of the foundation (see the settlements curves in Figure 7). Therefore, the
 217 gap formation mechanism does not only prevent the transmission of settlements to the structure (Deck and
 218 Singh, 2012; Franza and DeJong, 2019) but also angular distortions.

219 A similar comparison in terms of maximum tensile strains $\varepsilon_{t,max}$, as a damage indicator, is shown
 220 in Figure 9. Four approaches are adopted for the tensile strain. In the advanced models, $\varepsilon_{t,max}$ values are
 221 directly obtained for each infill panel as an output of the analysis, at all storey elevations. For both advanced
 222 and simplified interaction models as well as greenfield analyses, tensile strains are estimated using the
 223 angular distortion β based method: namely, approximate estimates are obtained assuming $\varepsilon_{t,max} \approx \alpha \times \beta/2$
 224 that modifies the average shear of the panel by introducing the coefficient $\alpha = 2$ to account for the slab

225 fixity at the edges (Son and Cording, 2005; Boone, 1996). In the interaction models, β is estimated from
 226 the corner displacements of bays in Plaxis, the shear engineering strain of the Timoshenko beam, and as the
 227 greenfield slope S_{gf} in the greenfield analysis.

228 Figure 9 indicates that the infill stiffness is capable to decrease the category of damage of the low-
 229 rise buildings, preventing to reach the deformations levels experienced by the frames with flexible infills
 230 ($\varepsilon_{t,max} = 0.075 - 0.3\%$) associated with the damage categories "slight" to "moderate" (Mair et al., 1996).
 231 More importantly, comparing direct and β -based strains obtained from advanced modelling, this figure
 232 demonstrates that using approximate tensile strain inferred from β is effective for both flexible and stiff
 233 infills in low-rise buildings. This confirms that the angular distortion is an effective deformation parameter
 234 for framed structures, although infills at different elevations within a given bay undergo slightly different
 235 distribution, as displayed by Figure 10. This aspect is particularly of interest in medium-rise buildings, as
 236 later discussed in the text.

237 Also, Figure 9 shows that equivalent Timoshenko beam models associated with the two-stage analysis
 238 approach provide a trend of $\varepsilon_{t,max}$ in qualitative agreement with the advanced model using solid elements
 239 for the building, validating in this way the use of the equivalent Timoshenko beam for the estimate of both
 240 tunnelling-induced displacements and structural strains.

Figure 8: Plaxis and ASRE angular distortion (FRs2e0L)

Figure 9: Plaxis and ASRE tensile strain (FRs2e0L)

Figure 10: Contours of tensile strains in the infills panels of the long central two-storey frame (FRs2e0L) with (left) fully flexible panels, (right) stiff panels at: (a) $V_{lt} = 1.0\%$ and (b) $V_{lt} = 2.0\%$.

241 5.2. Influence of infills on the behaviour of medium-rise frames

242 Previous research has often addressed low-rise framed buildings, despite the frequent presence of
243 medium-rise frames in urban areas. The response to tunnelling of medium-rise frames is possibly more
244 complex because of the uneven distribution of deformations with the building height. Figure 11 shows
245 the tunnelling-induced settlements of the central five-storey structure S5e0L subjected to the effects of the
246 volume loss $V_{l,t} = 1$ and 2%, while angular distortions of bays and maximum tensile strains of panels are
247 detailed in Figures 12 and 13, respectively. Finally, contours of the tensile strains are reported in Figure 14.

248 Although the stiffness of the frame is capable to affect the interaction settlements in Figures 11a and
249 c, the infill stiffness leads to a nearly rigid response of the building that undergoes nearly uniform settle-
250 ments (see Figures 11b and d) and minimal distortions or strains if compared with the greenfield case (see
251 subplots b and d in Figures 12 and 13). Interestingly, maximum values in Figure 13 and distribution of
252 tensile strains at the ground level (i.e. 1st storey) infills in Figure 14 differ slightly from those of the upper
253 elevations (i.e. 2nd to nth storey), particularly in the presence of the flexible infills. For bare frames this
254 phenomenon was well described by experimental evidence by Xu et al. (2020); it is due to the continu-
255 ous interaction with the ground at the foundation level through pressure redistribution, which differs from
256 the mechanism at the upper storeys of bare frames that only interacts with the lower part of the buildings
257 through the columns/walls. On the other hand, tensile strains are more uniform along the building height
258 for stiff panels due to the panel reaction to the redistribution of vertical pressure beneath the foundation.

259 Regarding the performance of simplified modelling, as shown in Figure 8, the ASRE EP results display
260 a good accuracy for the estimate of the bay angular distortion when compared with the advance model, for
261 both flexible and stiff infills. Similarly, when adopting the β -method to calculate the infill tensile strains
262 from the shear strains γ , ASRE EP and Plaxis values are almost coincident at the ground level infills (see
263 Figure 13); this is due to the Timoshenko beam axis continuously interacting with the soil, similarly to the
264 raft foundation of frames.

Figure 11: Plaxis and ASRE foundation settlements for the five-storey long frame (FRs5e0L).

Figure 12: Plaxis and ASRE angular distortion (FRs5e0L)

Figure 13: Plaxis and ASRE tensile strain (FRs5e0L)

Figure 14: Contours of tensile strains in the infills panels of the long central two-storey frame (FRs2e0L) at $V_{it} = 2.0\%$: (left) fully flexible panels, (right) stiff panels.

265 5.3. Results for eccentric buildings

266 As expected, eccentricity affects significantly settlements and deformations of buildings. Figures 15 and
 267 16 show foundation vertical displacements of the low-rise frames for tunnel excavations with eccentricity
 268 $e/B = 0.2$ and 0.5 , respectively. Similarly, Figures 17 and 18 refer to the five-storey case. In these figures,
 269 as for centrally located tunnels, the infill stiffening action resulted in the reduction of the maximum settle-
 270 ment and slope, with a decrease in the transmission of greenfield displacements to the building. Importantly,
 271 the simple models relying on the Timoshenko beam solution provide a reasonable estimate of the interac-
 272 tion settlements predicted by the advanced model also for eccentric buildings, despite some differences in
 273 specific scenarios. For example, see Figure 15, at the foundation edge close to the tunnel or the slightly
 274 larger deflection for the portion of the building above the tunnel when $e/B = 0.2$.

275 Next, the eccentricity impact on building deformations is addressed. Figure 19 reports the tunnelling-
 276 induced angular distortion β of the eccentric two-storey buildings 2Se02L and 2Se05L (whose settlements
 277 are given in Figures 15 and 16). For the sake of brevity, only two-storey buildings are analysed in detail.
 278 Also, tensile strains of 2Se02L and 2Se05L are well approximated by the β approach and, thus, $\varepsilon_{t,max}$
 279 distributions are reported in supplemental data.

Figure 15: Plaxis and ASRE foundation settlements for the two storey long frame at the eccentricity $e/B = 0.2$ (FRs2e02L)

Figure 16: Plaxis and ASRE foundation settlements for the two storey long frame at the eccentricity $e/B = 0.5$ (FRs2e05L)

280 Figure 19 indicates that the presence of the stiff infills attenuates the distortion amplitude. However, its
 281 distribution (i.e. shape of curves) is highly dependent on the eccentricity, for both flexible and stiff infills.
 282 In fact, in Figure 19, the distortion β of frame 2Se02L with $e/B = 0.2$ has a shape similar to the results for
 283 the central configuration 2Se0L ($e/B = 0$) in Figure 8, with β changing sign only in correspondence of the
 284 centreline ($x = 0$). On the other hand, the angular distortion trend in the building 2Se05L (with $e/B = 0.5$)
 285 changes sign around the inflection point of the greenfield settlement trough; this resulted in rather limited

Figure 17: Plaxis and ASRE foundation settlements for the five storey long frame at the eccentricity $e/B = 0.2$ (FRs5e02L)

Figure 18: Plaxis and ASRE foundation settlements for the five storey long frame at the eccentricity $e/B = 0.5$ (FRs5e05L)

286 absolute values of β . To clarify this mechanism, building slope S and local tilt w (defined in Figure 2),
 287 inferred from the Plaxis results for these two eccentric configurations, are shown in Figure 20. The tilt w
 288 is nearly uniform across the building and it is (approximately) an average value of S . Because S changes
 289 of sign for $e/B = 0.2$, the amplitude of the tilt w is rather small and its effect on the angular distortion
 290 $\beta = S - w$ is minor. On the other hand, S has a constant sign for $e/B = 0.5$ and it results in a local tilt w
 291 that is nearly half the maximum slope; consequently its impact on $\beta = S - w$ is notable. This mechanism
 292 is partly responsible for the decrease in β with the tunnel eccentricity, which is quantified by the proposed
 293 meta-model.

Figure 19: Plaxis and ASRE angular distortion of two-storey eccentric buildings (FRs2e02L,FRs2e05L)

Figure 20: Plaxis slope and local tilt of two-storey eccentric buildings (FRs2e02L,FRs2e05L)

294 5.4. Angular distortion for tensile strain prediction

295 The efficiency of the prediction of the maximum tensile strain within the infills of the frame by the use
 296 of angular distortion was evaluated in Figures 9 and 13 for central structures. Figure 21 displays $\varepsilon_{t,max}$
 297 plotted against $\alpha \times \beta/2$ for $V_{l,t} = 0.4$ and 1% for the entire dataset of case studies (see Table 1) using the
 298 advanced numerical simulations. This figure confirms that, for both stiff and flexible infills, the angular
 299 distortion of a bay is a good proxy for assessing the strain level for any building eccentricity. However, a
 300 slight overestimate of the tensile strains (i.e. $\alpha \times \beta/2 > \varepsilon_{t,max}$) is notable at the highest deformation level,
 301 likely due to the presence of a gap formation affecting the distortions of 1st storey infills at the ground level.

Figure 21: Evaluation of the tensile strain predictions in frames with (top) stiff and (bottom) flexible infills: estimated from $\alpha = 2$ against calculated numerical values for $V_{l,t} = 0.4\%$ and 1%.

302 6. Meta-model for predicting the tunnelling-induced SSI of infilled frames

303 For preliminary risk assessments a methodology is needed to estimate the tunnelling-induced angular
304 distortion and, then, infer infill deformations. For bare frames, [Xu et al. \(2021b\)](#) and [Xu et al. \(2020\)](#) sug-
305 gested to link the angular distortion modification factor $M^\beta = \beta_{max}/S_{gf,max}$ (given by the ratio between the
306 maximum angular distortion of the building and the maximum average greenfield slope, both defined with
307 respect to the building bays) to the relative stiffness parameter $\kappa = E_s B/GA_s^*$ (depending on the building
308 shear stiffness GA_s^* per running meter, the representative soil Young's modulus E_s and the building trans-
309 verse length B). Also, [Xu et al. \(2021b\)](#) and [Xu et al. \(2020\)](#) empirically observed that M^β decreases with
310 the normalised eccentricity e/B . However, no guidance is currently available for frames with stiff panels
311 contributing to the interaction problem.

312 For both bare and infilled frames, the unified meta-model described by Equations (3) and (4) is proposed,
313 providing the modification factor M^β as a function of the relative soil-structure stiffness κ . This meta-
314 model represents a semi-analytical method, in which the results of ASRE, interaction model based on the
315 elastic continuum and the Timoshenko beam theories, are corrected through an empirical factor to account
316 for the effect of building eccentricity, observed in the previous section. Similar analytical expressions
317 describing modification factors obtained from elastic interaction models were presented, among others, for
318 pipelines ([Klar et al., 2005](#)), tunnels ([Yu et al., 2022](#)), and buildings ([El Kahi et al., 2020](#)). The meta-model
319 relies on the following assumptions: 1) the parameter κ is applicable to both bare and infilled frames; 2)
320 $M^\beta \approx S_{max}/S_{gf,max} - w/S_{gf,max}$ follows from the angular distortion definition $\beta = S - w$ as the difference
321 between bay slope and tilt, by considering maximum greenfield slope and angular distortion correspond to a
322 given bay and by normalising both terms of this definition by $S_{gf,max}$; 3) the tilt of all bays as the result of the
323 interaction w may be approximated by the average greenfield slope at the building edges ω_{gf} ; 4) the frame
324 stiffening action can be always characterised by the response of a building centrally located above the tunnel,
325 from which it follows that the modification factor for a centrally located building is $R = S_{max}/S_{gf,max}$. In
326 particular, it is proposed to approximate M^β by a function of κ and e/B , for both bare and infilled frames,
327 through the following relationships:

$$M^\beta = R \left(1 - \frac{\omega_{gf}}{S_{gf,max}} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$R = 0.5 \tanh(1.08 \log_{10} \kappa - 1.31) + 0.5; \quad (4)$$

328 where R is the function of κ describing for central structures (with $e/B = 0$) the reduction in modification
 329 factor M^β with the relative stiffness. More specifically, the term between brackets accounts for the reduction
 330 in modification factor that is assumed linearly proportional to the tilt-to-maximum greenfield ground slope
 331 ratio. The relationship in Equation (4) describing R is obtained from the regression of the results of a
 332 parametric study carried out with the elastic (EL) two-stage approach using the ASRE model of Timoshenko
 333 beam centrally placed above the tunnel ($e/B = 0$) and with a shear-dominated flexibility subjected to a
 334 tunnelling-induced settlement trough defined by a standard Gaussian curve having inflection point offset i
 335 and building width-to-inflection point ratio $B/i = 10$, in other words extending beyond the tunnel influence
 336 area. Equation (4) provides a nearly perfect match with the interaction model results. The use of the elastic
 337 (EL) model is conservative with respect to elastoplastic (EP) predictions at medium-to-high volume losses,
 338 associated with the potential for soil yielding and gap formation at the soil-foundation interface.

339 The efficiency of κ for frames with stiff infills (i.e. assumption 1) in predicting M^β is first evaluated.
 340 Figure 22 displays M^β plotted against κ for the infilled frames analysed in this paper ($V_{l,t} = 0.4$ and 1%)
 341 as well as for the centrifuge (Xu et al., 2020) and numerical results (Boldini et al., 2021a) of bare frames
 342 ($V_{l,t} = 1\%$). Results distinguished for varying eccentricity e/B indicates consistent trends between infilled
 343 and bare structures, thus confirming the applicability of k also to infilled frames. Also, Figure 22 shows
 344 that a reduction in M^β with e/B occurs for both infilled and bare frames, this phenomenon being compatible
 345 with assumption 2.

346 The predictions achieved by using the ASRE-based R in Equation (4), strictly applicable to $e/B = 0$,
 347 are also shown in Figure 22. The term R is capable to fit well M^β of the central buildings (Figure 22a),
 348 proving the robustness of the proposed expression. However, R in Equation (4) overestimates the value of
 349 M^β associated with flexible and semi-flexible eccentric buildings, as shown in Figures 22b and c. Thus, R
 350 should be reduced for eccentric buildings.

351 To evaluate the efficiency of the meta-model given by Equations (3) and (4), the *corrected modification*
 352 *factor* is introduced as $M^{\beta,cor} = M^\beta + R\omega_{gf}/S_{gf,max}$, obtained by rearranging Equation (3). The physical
 353 meaning of $M^{\beta,cor}$ is being the modification factor that an eccentric building would display if centrally
 354 located above the tunnel; when $M^{\beta,cor} \approx R$ in the validation later discussed, it follows that Equation (3)
 355 should be considered appropriate. Figure 23 summarises the values of $M^{\beta,cor}$ for the infilled and bare frames
 356 considered in Figure 22. The agreement between $M^{\beta,cor}$ and R is satisfactory and it can be stated that the
 357 reducing effect of the building eccentricity (that relates to the input global tilt ω as well as the resulting

358 local tilt w) on the modification factor and, consequently, the soil-structure interaction is well captured by
 359 the term $R\omega_{gf}/S_{gf,max}$.

Figure 22: Modification factor M^β against relative soil-structure stiffness: (a) $e/B = 0$; (b) $e/B = 0.2$; (c) $e/B = 0.5$;

Figure 23: Corrected modification factor $M^{\beta,cor}$ against relative soil-structure stiffness: (a) $e/B = 0$; (b) $e/B = 0.2$; (c) $e/B = 0.5$;

360 In order to directly evaluate the efficiency of the meta-model, the approximated modification factor
 361 $R(1 - \omega_{gf}/S_{gf,max})$ estimated using Equations (3) and (4) is directly compared against exact model results
 362 in Figure 24, in which the 1:1 line indicates a perfect match. The meta-model provides, for the considered
 363 infilled and bare frames, a good assessment in the case of fully-flexible and rigid structures. In contrast,
 364 conservative estimates are predicted when the buildings undergo a semi-flexible response (i.e. $0.1 < M^\beta <$
 365 0.9) under most cases.

366 Note that an in-depth analysis of the full dataset also indicates that: (i) the meta-model prediction tends
 367 to become overconservative at high volume losses (with $V_{l,t} \geq 2\%$) for the semi-flexible buildings (with
 368 $M^\beta = 0.1 - 0.6$), due to the fact that the meta-model does not consider the gap formation and its effect
 369 on the transmission of the ground movements (figures omitted for brevity); (ii) the efficiency of the meta-
 370 model decreased when adopting the interaction local tilt w or average edge slope ω instead of ω_{gf} (see
 371 supplemental data). The latter point confirmed that the use of ω_{gf} to quantify the impact of the building tilt

372 in the meta-model is appropriate.

Figure 24: Evaluation of the meta-model predictions: estimated against calculated numerical values.

373 Finally, the use of the elastic EL approach (point i) instead of the EP solutions for the development of the
 374 meta-model should be discussed. The Linear elastic approach lead to conservative predictions and allows
 375 to limit the number of inputs required by the meta-model. In fact, the development of a meta-model based
 376 on the EP solution would require as input both the building average contact pressure and the tunnel volume
 377 loss level, together with a more complex regression formula to capture the highly nonlinear effects of the
 378 gap on the interaction; thus, for the sake of ease-of-use in practice, the elastic EL model was preferred.

379 With respect to the meta-model applicability, its validation is performed against results for frames with
 380 continuous foundations, when horizontal foundation strains are negligible (Xu et al., 2020). For frames
 381 with separate footings, the additional detrimental effect of horizontal differential displacements along the
 382 foundation should be considered; using engineering judgement, conservative estimate of the foundation
 383 horizontal strain may be inferred from the corresponding modification factor estimate by previous work for
 384 bare frames on separate footings (Boldini et al., 2021a; Xu et al., 2021a).

385 7. Conclusions

386 This numerical study investigates the tunnelling-induced response of low- and medium-rise framed
 387 buildings with either fully-flexible or stiff infill panels with continuous foundations; results for flexible in-
 388 fills describe the response of bare frames. In particular, the outcomes of advanced 3D Finite Element anal-
 389 yses are compared with two-stage analytical solutions adopting equivalent Timoshenko beams. Tunnelling-
 390 induced foundation displacements, average angular distortions of bays, and maximum tensile strains in the
 391 infills are calculated for different building configurations and eccentricity, while the deformation parameters
 392 are analysed in the context of risk assessments. Independently of the numerical approach, it was confirmed

393 that the stiffening contribution of infills is fundamental in altering the soil-structure interaction and limiting
394 structural damage. The following main conclusions are drawn.

- 395 • In a preliminary assessment stage, Timoshenko beams dominated by shear deformations can be suc-
396 cessfully used in the analysis of soil-structure interaction problems of tunnelling beneath framed
397 buildings that have continuous foundations transversely to the tunnel, both as equivalent structural
398 models in simplified FE analyses and as a tool for predicting the expected damage. For this, analyti-
399 cal approaches to quickly estimate the equivalent bending and shear stiffness of both bare and infilled
400 frames were suggested.
- 401 • The two-stage approach implementing an equivalent Timoshenko beam founded on the half-space
402 (firstly suggested by [Franza et al. \(2020\)](#) for bearing wall masonry buildings) is a robust and straight-
403 forward modelling technique also for low- and medium-rise framed buildings affected by tunnelling,
404 for both no infills and stiff infills without openings.
- 405 • This work is linked to previous research to contribute towards a unique framework for framed building
406 damage assessment when affected by tunnelling. This study proved that the use of relative soil-shear
407 stiffness factor and modification factors of angular distortions (suggested by [Xu et al. \(2020\)](#) for bare
408 frames) is also applicable to infilled frames. Also, the reliability of estimating the tunnelling-induced
409 maximum tensile strain of infills from bay angular distortions, corrected with a coefficient for the
410 slab edge fixity ([Boone, 1996](#)), was found to work properly in this numerical study for both low- and
411 medium-rise frames.
- 412 • A new meta-model was proposed with a semi-analytical approach to predict the maximum angu-
413 lar distortion of bare and infilled frames from greenfield settlements, eccentricity, and relative soil-
414 structure stiffness. Together with the distortion-based estimate of the tensile strains, it can be imple-
415 mented in effective risk assessments. In details, this meta-model consists in a reduction of the angular
416 distortion modification factor of central structures, obtained from linear elastic interaction models,
417 that is proportional to the ratio between average and maximum greenfield ground slopes; thus, it pro-
418 vides insights into structural deformation mechanics by quantifying the relationship between relative
419 soil-building stiffness and building tilt.

420 In this work, numerical simulations considered the presence of linear elastic infills perfectly bounded to the
421 frame. However, tunnelling-induced damage of panels may depend on the connection conditions between

422 frame and infills as well as masonry nonlinear behaviour (at the pre- and post-cracking state). Future
423 research should address these aspects, the relationship between angular distortion of bays and infills strains
424 in the presence of openings, and the stiffening effect of infills on the differential horizontal displacements
425 of infilled frames with separate footings.

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430 References

- 431 Acikgoz, S., Luciano, A., Dewhirst, M., DeJong, M.J., Mair, R., 2021. Innovative monitoring of the response of a heritage masonry
432 building to nearby tunnelling in London Clay. *Géotechnique*, 1–16 URL: <https://www.icevirtuallibrary.com/doi/10.1680/jgeot.19.P.243>, doi:10.1680/jgeot.19.P.243.
- 434 Boldini, D., Losacco, N., Bertolin, S., Amorosi, A., 2018. Finite Element modelling of tunnelling-induced displacements on
435 framed structures. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology* 80, 222–231. doi:10.1016/j.tust.2018.06.019.
- 436 Boldini, D., Losacco, N., Franza, A., DeJong, M.J., Xu, J., Marshall, A.M., 2021a. Tunneling-induced deformation of bare frame
437 structures on sand: numerical study of building deformations. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering* 147,
438 04021116. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002627.
- 439 Boldini, D., Losacco, N., Franza, A., Miraei, S., 2021b. Numerical modelling of framed structures with masonry infills affected by
440 tunnelling-induced deformation and damage, in: Elshafie, M.Z., Viggiani, G.M., Mair, R.J. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ISSMGE*
441 *TC204-Symposium (IS-Cambridge 2020)*, CRC Press, Cambridge, UK. pp. 510–516. URL: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/9781000421095/chapters/10.1201/9780429321559-66>, doi:10.1201/9780429321559-66.
- 443 Boldini, D., Losacco, N., Franza, A., Miraei, S., 2021c. Tunnelling-induced displacements and damage on framed structures:
444 comparison between numerical models, in: *International Conference of the International Association for Computer Methods*
445 *and Advances in Geomechanics: Challenges and Innovations in Geomechanics*, Turin, Italy. pp. 148–155. doi:10.1007/
446 978-3-030-64518-2_18.
- 447 Boone, S.J., 1996. Ground-Movement-Related Building Damage. *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering* 122, 886–896. doi:10.
448 1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1996)122:11(886).
- 449 Burland, J.B., Broms, B.B., De Mello, V.F.B., 1977. Behaviour of foundations and structures, in: *Proceedings of the 9th Interna-*
450 *tional Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundations Engineering*, Tokyo. pp. 495–546.
- 451 Dafalias, Y.F., Manzari, M.T., 2004. Simple Plasticity Sand Model Accounting for Fabric Change Effects. *Journal of Engineering*
452 *Mechanics* 130, 622–634. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9399(2004)130:6(622).
- 453 Deck, O., Singh, A., 2012. Analytical model for the prediction of building deflections induced by ground movements. *International*
454 *Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics* 36, 62–84. doi:10.1002/nag.993.
- 455 El Kahi, E., Deck, O., Khouri, M., Mehdizadeh, R., Rahme, P., 2020. A new simplified meta-model to evaluate the trans-
456 mission of ground movements to structures integrating the elastoplastic soil behavior. *Structures* 23, 324–334. URL:
457 <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2352012419301948>, doi:10.1016/j.istruc.2019.10.023.
- 458 Elkayam, I., Klar, A., 2019. Nonlinear elasto-plastic formulation for tunneling effects on superstructures. *Canadian Geotechnical*
459 *Journal* 56, 956–969. doi:10.1139/cgj-2018-0021.
- 460 Fagnoli, V., Gragnano, C.G., Boldini, D., Amorosi, A., 2015. 3D numerical modelling of soil–structure interaction during EPB
461 tunnelling. *Géotechnique* 65, 23–37. doi:10.1680/geot.14.P.091.
- 462 Finno, R.J., Voss, F.T., Rossow, E., Blackburn, J.T., 2005. Evaluating Damage Potential in Buildings Affected by Excavations.
463 *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering* 131, 1199–1210. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2005)131:
464 10(1199).
- 465 Franza, A., Acikgoz, S., DeJong, M.J., 2020. Timoshenko beam models for the coupled analysis of building response to tunnelling.
466 *Tunneling and Underground Construction* 96, 103160. doi:10.1016/j.tust.2019.103160.
- 467 Franza, A., DeJong, M.J., 2019. Elastoplastic solutions to predict tunneling-induced load redistribution and deformation of surface
468 structures. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering* 145, 04019007. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.
469 0002021.
- 470 Franzius, J.N., Potts, D.M., Burland, J.B., 2006. The response of surface structures to tunnel construction. *Proceedings of the ICE*
471 *- Geotechnical Engineering* 159, 3–17. doi:10.1680/geng.2006.159.1.3.

- 472 Fu, J., Yu, Z., Wang, S., Yang, J., 2018. Numerical analysis of framed building response to tunnelling induced ground movements.
473 Engineering Structures 158, 43–66. doi:10.1016/j.engstruct.2017.11.039.
- 474 Giardina, G., Losacco, N., DeJong, M.J., Viggiani, G.M.B., Mair, R.J., 2020. Effect of soil models on the prediction of tunnelling-
475 induced deformations of structures. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Geotechnical Engineering 173, 379–397.
476 doi:10.1680/jgeen.18.00127.
- 477 Goh, K.H., Mair, R.J., 2014. Response of framed buildings to excavation-induced movements. Soils and Foundations 54, 250–268.
478 doi:10.1016/j.sandf.2014.04.002.
- 479 Haji, T.K., Marshall, A.M., Tizani, W., 2018. A cantilever approach to estimate bending stiffness of buildings affected by tunnelling.
480 Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology 71, 47–61. doi:10.1016/j.tust.2017.08.005.
- 481 Klar, A., Vorster, T.E.B., Soga, K., Mair, R.J., 2005. Soil-pipe interaction due to tunnelling : comparison between Winkler and
482 elastic continuum solutions. Géotechnique 55, 461–466.
- 483 Losacco, N., Burghignoli, A., Callisto, L., 2014. Uncoupled evaluation of the structural damage induced by tunnelling.
484 Géotechnique 64, 646–656. doi:10.1680/geot.13.P.213.
- 485 Losacco, N., Callisto, L., Burghignoli, A., 2016. Soil-structure interaction due to tunnelling in soft ground, an equivalent solid
486 approach, in: Van Balen, K., Verstryngge, E. (Eds.), Structural Analysis of Historical Constructions, CRC Press. pp. 495–501.
487 doi:10.1201/9781315616995-74.
- 488 Mair, R.J., Taylor, R.N., Burland, J.B., 1996. Prediction of ground movements and assessment of risk of building damage due to
489 bored tunnelling, in: Mair, R.J., Taylor, R.N. (Eds.), Proceedings of the International Symposium on Geotechnical Aspects of
490 Underground Construction in Soft Ground, Balkema, Rotterdam, London, United Kingdom. pp. 713–718.
- 491 Melis, M.J., Rodriguez Ortiz, J.M., 2001. Consideration of the stiffness of buildings in the estimation of subsidence damage
492 by EPB tunnelling in the Madrid subway, in: Jardine, F.M. (Ed.), Proceedings of the international conference on response of
493 buildings to excavation induced ground movements, Ciria Special Publication 201, London, UK. pp. 387–394.
- 494 Picciullo, L., Ritter, S., Lysdahl, A.O.K., Langford, J., Nadim, F., 2021. Assessment of building damage due to excavation-induced
495 displacements: The GIBV method. Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology 108, 103673. doi:10.1016/j.tust.
496 2020.103673.
- 497 Pikhaver, J., Burd, H., Houlsby, G., 2010. An equivalent beam method to model masonry buildings in 3D finite element analysis.
498 Computers Structures 88, 1049–1063. doi:10.1016/j.compstruc.2010.05.006.
- 499 Ritter, S., 2017. Experiments in tunnel-soil-structure interaction. Ph.D. thesis, University of Cambridge doi:10.17863/CAM.
500 20966.
- 501 Ritter, S., DeJong, M., Giardina, G., 2019. Experimental evaluation of analytical methods to assess building response to tunnelling
502 subsidence. Geomechanics and Tunnelling 12, 499–504. URL: [https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/geot.](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/geot.201900025)
503 [201900025](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/geot.201900025), doi:10.1002/geot.201900025.
- 504 Ritter, S., Giardina, G.G., Franza, A., DeJong, M.J., 2020. Building Deformation Caused by Tunneling: Centrifuge Modeling.
505 Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering 146, 04020017. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002223.
- 506 Son, M., 2015. Response analysis of nearby structures to tunneling-induced ground movements in sandy soils. Tunnelling and
507 Underground Space Technology 48, 156–169. doi:10.1016/j.tust.2015.03.008.
- 508 Son, M., Cording, E.J., 2005. Estimation of building damage due to excavation-induced ground movements. Journal of Geotech-
509 nical and Geoenvironmental Engineering 131, 162–177. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2005)131:2(162).
- 510 Xu, J., Franza, A., Marshall, A., Losacco, N., 2021a. Role of footing embedment on tunnel-foundation interaction. Journal of
511 Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering 147, 06021009. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002603.
- 512 Xu, J., Franza, A., Marshall, A.M., 2020. Response of framed buildings on raft foundations to tunneling. Journal of Geotechnical
513 and Geoenvironmental Engineering 146, 04020120. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002376.
- 514 Xu, J., Franza, A., Marshall, A.M., Losacco, N., Boldini, D., 2021b. Tunnel-framed building interaction: comparison between raft
515 and separate footing foundations. Géotechnique 71, 631–644. doi:10.1680/jgeot.19.P.393.
- 516 Yiu, W.N., Burd, H.J., Martin, C.M., 2017. Finite-element modelling for the assessment of tunnel-induced damage to a masonry
517 building. Géotechnique 67, 780–794. doi:10.1680/jgeot.sip17.P.249.
- 518 Yu, J., Li, H., Huang, M., Li, Y., Tan, J.Q.W., Guo, Y., 2022. Timoshenko-beam-based response of existing tunnel to single
519 tunneling underneath and numerical verification of opening and dislocation. Computers and Geotechnics 147, 104757. doi:10.
520 1016/j.compgeo.2022.104757.